

Grant agreement no. 312788

<http://odin-project.eu>

D6.2 International validation of project outputs

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Abstract: In this report, we have presented how ODIN interoperability approach aligns with other international activities in this area. In addition, we have discussed how the collaboration between DataCite, ORCID and other ODIN partners has initiated a number of activities towards building a layer of interoperability between identifiers. The scope of these activities highlights the importance and versatility of ODIN interoperability model, and suggests that presented results can be further developed to benefit the extended community. With the integration of the

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international partners the project has been participating and engaging in discussions beyond the traditional scope, i.e. with global 3rd party services. The insights from the international partners also helped to enrich the disciplinary discussions within the project to study beyond the proofs of concept and provide “hands-on” experience from other communities.

ODIN gap analysis and roadmap shows that there are a number of areas that requires planning and special attention of policy makers, research institutions and funding bodies in order to create a seamless integration of identifiers into research ecosystems. As discussed in this report, the experience by ANDS and other international partners show that there is a need for developing technical capabilities, best practice approaches and training for the research community to enable using unique identifiers and use these identifiers to link the scholarly work. The gap analysis by ODIN partners provided a cohesive list of requirements for future development of e-infrastructure and interoperability projects in the research sector.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report provides an international perspective to the ODIN outcomes including the application of the ODIN interoperability model to research data infrastructures in Australia and US. In addition, the authors describe aligned international activities with ODIN outcomes.

Publications and research data are the steam engine of the research enterprise. Each year, billions of Euros of taxpayers' money and philanthropic contributions enable new research projects across the world. However, despite this significant investment in research and innovation, there is an infrastructure gap for enabling the reuse of research and research data. The vision of scientific community that does not waste resources on recreating research data has been the objective of many policy makers and funding agencies. Vice-President of the EU Commission and Responsible for the Digital Agenda, Neelie Kroes envisages such a community in the introduction of the Final Report of the High Level Expert Group on Scientific Data [5].

Interoperability between research infrastructures is a key enabler in making research and research data reusable as it supports the discoverability of research data, and data sharing. The key component in enabling interoperability is implementing persistent identifiers. The ODIN project has played a significant role in this domain by promoting two global identifiers, ORCID and DataCite, and facilitating a number of international activities based on the interoperability of these global identifiers.

The problem under analysis by ODIN is global and it requires transnational solutions. The ODIN project was therefore expressly designed to have international participation in order to ensure that this European-funded interoperability initiative was in fact globally relevant, supported by global infrastructures, and informed by

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diverse international use cases. This workpackage (WP6) is meant to validate the ODIN approach from an international perspective, thus mitigating the risk of promoting a parochial approach.

The goal of the ODIN project is to address the issue of interoperability by investigating and resolving issues related to the persistent identifiers. As part of this project, international partners (ANDS, arXiv and Dryad) are investigating how the proposed ODIN solutions address the concerns of the international audience, and how the proposed interoperability model can be extended beyond the ODIN proof-of-concept projects.

ODIN's approach is to adopt existing national schemes that can be interlinked with a coherent global framework, with each nation's local knowledge and strongly-grounded infrastructures serving as the sustainable substrate of the global scheme. This is realized by DataCite's structure, with members in 14 different countries, each serving a local network of members. For example, at the time of writing, 23 Australian research institutions are taking advantage of ANDS services to assign DOIs to datasets through DataCite. Dryad mints DOIs through the EZID service at the California Digital Library, which currently has dozens of other clients, mostly in the US. arXiv similarly has plans to assign DOIs for datasets.

ORCID is also a strongly international organization, with many dozens of members from a variety of different stakeholder groups. ANDS has integrated ORCIDs into its researcher identity system and there are a number of ANDS-ORCID activities planned for 2013-15 including joint webinars, community building, policy development, and systems integration [3]. Dryad has initiated efforts toward integration of ORCIDs into DSpace, the widely used open source institutional repository platform [4].

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A number of funders, both public and private, are members of ORCID, including those from outside Europe such as the US National Institutes of Health and the Japan Science and Technology Agency. ANDS has initiated a discussion with Australian research funders to incorporate the ODIN approach on researcher identifiers by using ORCID as the identifier for the applicants and grantees. In the US, NSF and NIH have modified their biosketch guidelines for applicants, allowing data to be listed as scholarly products of relevance for evaluation, and the NIH has directly integrated ORCID identifiers into its new SciENcv system¹.

Research institutions are beginning to incorporate persistent identifiers for researchers and data into their systems and processes. ORCID received funding from the Sloan Foundation to competitively award support for adoption and integration to nine different organizations in the US, not just for reporting but also researcher-facing data platforms such as nanoHub and Reactome. ANDS has worked with research organisations in Australia to promote awareness of the ODIN approach to allocating ORCID identifiers to researchers who create data as an output of their project. Technical integration and interoperability with ANDS systems is under development (see below) and broad community support activities have been initiated. These activities are aligned with and informed by the ODIN WP5 roadmap and gap analysis which highlights the need for cultural change, support and training, as well as easy to use researcher facing tools that remove the complexity of the underlying systems.

The ODIN project international partners have already had significant input into all ODIN work packages. This report (ODIN Deliverable 6.2) discusses the ODIN proof-of-concept projects, proposed frameworks and roadmaps (WP3, WP4 and WP5). Some of ODIN's achievements such as the roadmap for identifiers, interoperability challenges, aggregation of metadata descriptions and trust have been enabled by

¹ http://www.nlm.nih.gov/pubs/techbull/so13/so13_sciencv.html

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efforts across multiple working packages. These achievements are not only important to ODIN partners but have a significant value to the wider community who work on research data infrastructure. In the following sections of this report we will discuss some of the national and international activities that are aligned with ODIN outcomes, and we discuss the achievements from the individual work packages.

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2. INTERNATIONAL PARTNERS' PERSPECTIVES

A recent statement² by the G8 Science Ministers recognises the need for international collaborative efforts to enable global research infrastructure. Aligned with this statement, the ODIN project has contributed to the international collaborative efforts for interoperability among research infrastructures. Collaboration with international ODIN partners has fostered new activities that contribute to better discovery and reuse of research data, and reinforces actions taken by many different stakeholders internationally.

2.1. ANDS

ANDS has leveraged ODIN interoperability model and other ODIN achievements in the following domains.

Thomson Reuters DCI and Research Data Australia Interoperability Project

The ODIN ecosystem outlined in the WP5 roadmap depicts a global open interoperable identifier system as a powerful enabling infrastructure for third party services, products, and innovation. For example, the presence of a trusted DOI registrar for data has spurred and enabled the development of the Data Citation Index (DCI), a new product that is part of Thomson Reuters' Web of Science search and discovery platform. The DCI takes advantage of the accessible and standardized metadata from the wide variety of different DataCite clients³. In 2013, ANDS initiated a new interoperability project to integrate Research Data Australia (by ANDS) into the DCI. This project leverages the interoperability of identifiers including DataCite DOI

² <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/g8-science-ministers-statement>

³ <http://thomsonreuters.com/press-releases/082014/datacite-research-discovery>

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and ORCID, and it has benefited from ODIN interoperability approach to linking researchers and their research data.

ANDS engagement with Research Data Alliance Interoperability Projects

The ODIN approach on identifiers is already having impact through ANDS' engagement with the Research Data Alliance (RDA)⁴, a joint venture between the European Commission, the Australian Government through ANDS and the US National Science Foundation. ANDS' contribution to the RDA Data Description Registry Interoperability (DDRI) working group is focused on linking researchers to datasets and publication. Moreover, the projects in this work use the ORCID and DataCite APIs to search and link scholarly work. As part of the projects in this working group, ANDS closely follows ODIN's approach to interoperability for linking datasets, researchers and grants across Dryad, CERN and Research Data Australia. In addition, the interoperability between identifiers is a key component of other interoperability projects in this group including:

- NARCIS and Research Data Australia Interoperability Project
 - o DANS (dans.knaw.nl) promotes sustained access to digital research data, and encourages researchers to archive and reuse data in a sustained manner, e.g. through the online archiving system EASY. DANS also provides access, via NARCIS.nl, to thousands of multidisciplinary datasets, e-publications and other research information in the Netherlands.
 - o DANS and ANDS exploring an approach for metadata data exchange service between NARCIS and Research Data Australia. This project can leverage DataCite services and author identifiers as a platform for de-duplicating records between research data registries.

⁴ <https://rd-alliance.org>

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- VIVO Data Description Exchange Solution
 - o VIVO is a research-focused multidisciplinary discovery tool that enables collaboration among researchers across all disciplines. The VIVO project was initiated and resides in the Cornell University Library, with support from the Office of the Provost. In this work, Cornell University provides input into the interoperability between registries using linked data and VIVO ontology. Persistent identifiers including DOI and ORCID author identifiers are the key components of enabling linked data for research datasets.
- daJra and Data-PASS Interoperability Project
 - o DataPass: The Data Preservation Alliance for the Social Sciences (Data-PASS) is a voluntary partnership of organizations created to archive, catalog and preserve data used for social science research. Examples of social science data include: opinion polls; voting records; surveys on family growth and income; social network data; government statistics and indices; and GIS data measuring human activity. A National Digital Stewardship Alliance Founding Member, the Data-PASS partnership works to:
 - Archive social science data collections at-risk of being lost.
 - Catalog and promote access to archived collections in the Data-PASS shared catalog.
 - Replicated preservation of archived collections.
 - Advocate best practices in digital preservation.
 - o daJra is the DOI registration service in Germany (and beyond) for social and economic data jointly run by GESIS, a Leibniz Institute for Social Sciences, and the ZBW - Leibniz Information Centre for Economics. This infrastructure lays the foundation for long-term, persistent identification, storage, localization and reliable citation of research data. More than 20 clients have registered about 290.000 DOI names (last update February 2014). Every DOI name is linked to a

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comprehensive set of metadata, a collection of bibliographical and content information, which refer to the registered dataset (title, author, publication date, copyright etc.). These metadata are compliant with the DDI metadata standard and stored in the da|ra database. The da|ra service is provided in cooperation with DataCite, the international initiative to establish easier access to digital research data.

- o DataPass and da|ra are working on a metadata exchange solution across their platforms based on the DDI model and interoperability between identifiers. The proposed service can leverage DataCite services for enabling cross-platform discovery.
- DCU and DANS Interoperability Project
 - o The Digital Curation Unit (dcu.gr) is part of the Institute for the Management of Information Systems of the "Athena" Research and Innovation Centre in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies. DCU's mission is to conduct research, develop technologies and applications, provide services and training and act as a national focus point in the field of digital curation.

At the time of writing this report, DANS and DCU are working on a de-duplication service for humanity related research. The service will focus on author disambiguation and dataset de-duplication. This work enables interoperability between DCU and DANS using DataCite, ORCID and other identifier providers. Although this work is at the early stages, the ODIN strategy and gap analysis can lead to a better and more sustainable de-duplication service by this project.

ANDS integration into ORCID

ANDS has leveraged ORCID as a means for connecting research data collections to authors. Following collaboration with ODIN partners in developing the ODIN interoperability model, ANDS created an ORCID integration module that enables

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ORCID users to search and link their data collections from Research Data Australia (ANDS supported portal for Australian Research Data Common) to the user ORCID identifiers. The workflow for ANDS-ORCID integration is demonstrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. ANDS - ORCID integration model.

The workflow includes five steps:

- (1) the user initiates the Import Research Activity process from the ORCID login panel.
- (2) the ORCID web calls a webservice function from Research Data Australia (RDA) and provide RDA webservice with the user information.
- (3) RDA provides user with a search/wizard screen where users can find and confirm their datasets.
- (4) RDA sends the user back to ORCID web and provides ORCID services with the information about the user's datasets.

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(5) RDA records the links between the ORCID identifier and datasets in an open access repository.

Although the Australian research community is still in the early stages of adopting ORCID, the outcome of the ANDS-ORCID integration shows that ORCID identifier can be an effective method for connecting researchers and their research outcome.

Research Data Australia About Collections Parties Activities Services Themes

Search for Research Data

Advanced Search

Home / Bond University / Party

Michelle McLean

An undergraduate degree in Biological Sciences, followed by a Masters and PhD in plant and seed toxicology and mycology, I went on to obtain a Masters in Education. My interest in medical education began in the late 1990s when I was invited to be part of the Curriculum Development Task Force responsible for implementing a problem-based learning curriculum (University of Natal, which later became the University of KwaZulu-Natal). After several years as Head, Division of Histology, I was offered a post in Medical Education at the United Arab Emirates University. For almost 6 years, where I was largely involved in the first 4 years of the undergraduate medical programme, I took up a position as Academic Lead (Problem-based Learning) at Bond University. My research has largely revolved around student experiences in different parts of their training (e.g. the transition to the clinical environment, role models, impact of their gender, PBL, etc.).

Identifiers
 NLA: <http://nla.gov.au/nla.party-599356>
 ORCID: 0000-0002-9912-2483

Related Websites
 Personal Researcher Page at Bond University
 URI: http://works.bepress.com/michelle_mclean/

Access

Contacts
 Michelle_Mclean@bond.edu.au
 Bond University, Gold Coast,
 Queensland, 4229 Australia

Connections

Collections
 Medical student professional identity formation
 Generic skills development in undergraduate medical studies in a PBL programme

Contributed by

 Bond University

Figure 2. An example of a researcher record in Research Data Australia with connected ORCID identifier ⁵

⁵ <http://researchdata.ands.org.au/michelle-mclean/184000>

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Figure 2 shows an example of an ORCID identifier in Research Data Australia. This record has been curated by Bond University in Australia, and it has incorporated the ORCID identifier for the researcher leading to many related publications by this author. Given this record is already linked to two data collections (*Medical student professional identity formation*, and *Generic skills development in undergraduate medical studies in a PBL programme*), direct or indirect connectivity between these datasets and publication by authors can be established using third party software services. These kind of connectivities are the main focus of the ANDS interoperability projects in the Research Data Alliance, and the ODIN project has been a true guidance and enabler for the success stories in this domain.

2.2. Dryad

Dryad is a repository for research data. In Dryad's model, all the data files associated with a publication are grouped into a single "data package". Upon deposit, Dryad reserves DOIs for the datasets. They are minted for the data package as a whole and for each separate data file. The data package DOI is conveyed to the journal for inclusion in the published article. Dryad staff, partly manually and partly using automated processes, examines the data files for integrity, curate the metadata for completeness and quality, and may migrate files to preservation formats (see below). At the end of the process, there are cross-links between the published article and the data using identifiers that will continue to resolve even in the event of changes to the web address of the article and data.

Metadata challenges

One important metadata field that is currently too time-consuming to effectively curate is the author list. Currently, clustering and disambiguation of author names

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relies on error-prone lexical matches. A common core registry of ORCID profiles will provide Dryad with the ability to identify independent works by the same author both within the repository and in external bibliographic resources.

As part of ODIN we proposed to pilot the use of these identifiers within Dryad's submission and curation system. We can already anticipate some of the challenges. ORCID iDs will be conveyed by journals for each paper, authors may wish to add additional authors to a dataset, requiring functionality for depositors to quickly identify existing ORCID iDs for co-authors, or register new ones. There will be a many-to-one mapping between ORCID iDs and individuals. The accuracy and completeness of this ORCID database will slowly improve as it is used, but may not be initially impressive. Incorporating ORCID iDs into existing metadata standards, and web interfaces, will require some experimentation.

Funding information on Dryad and associated services

Dryad has collaborations with community specific journals with dedicated data policies requiring or supporting data deposition alongside the publication of a traditional textual article. In parallel, Dryad has been exploring sustainability measures in the past to understand how to provide community services in the long term. This results in a refined business models offering tailored pricing schemes for individual researchers, packages for journals or publishers or institutions. The latter for example includes a voucher model or memberships. Member journals or publishers can integrate the data submission into their workflows, which for example ensures bidirectional links (based on the PIDs) between the article and the data and increased visibility for both.

In an ideal case, one could imagine that the ORCID is integrated as author metadata already from a funder who issues a voucher for data submission to a grantee and, upon submission, gets the data and publication metadata returned from the journal

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or Dryad. It is future work to propagate such information from the funder to Dryad. However, first steps have been explored together with ANDS and CERN to understand how to accommodate the information in metadata schemas across disciplines and how to visualize such information networks. This has happened as part of the RDA Working Group on Data Description Registry Interoperability.

Dryad's engagement in third-party services

Dryad is getting more and more engaged in the provision of data to third party services, as well as shaping services serving the Open Science community. It is the aim to serve such services with good metadata, even though some of them might be outside the original scope of the Dryad data repository content. However, as more cross-disciplinary services develop, it is considered important to contribute to such initiatives.

One example are the forthcoming the altmetrics tools: (e.g., ImpactStory) which should allow more discoverability functionalities, e.g. using ORCID ID to get Dryad DOIs to get DataCite statistics. This is considered an important step when taking into account developments like the article level metrics⁶. PLOS released two new Article-Level Metrics (ALM) data sources: Europe PMC Database Citations and DataCite. Dryad feeds into the DataCite metadata store. The data from both sources are displayed on the metrics tab of PLOS articles, are available through the PLOS ALM API, and are available to all users of the open source ALM application.

Europe PMC Database Citations and DataCite are the first ALM sources that track research data that mention a particular PLOS article. We know from the work by Jo McEntyre and others at Europe PMC (see the May 2013 PLOS ONE article by Kafkas

⁶ <http://articlemetrics.github.io/blog/2013/12/05/research-findings-going-deeper-than-the-article>

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et al.) that the overlap between article-to-database citations and database-to-article citations is surprisingly small which underlines the need for more work in that regard.

PLOS and other publishers recognize that they need to do a better job helping authors to properly cite research data in their submitted manuscripts, and the recently published Draft Declaration of Data Citation Principles and the Force 11 principles are an excellent starting point. But providing the links from database-to-article as ALM can also increase the visibility of datasets associated with an article which feeds back to the Dryad community as well who shares data publicly as well.

Developments relevant for the Dryad community in its widest terms

EuropePMC has introduced a Graphical User Interface (GUI) for their advanced search that allows, among other things, discovery of articles that reference data, among them data coming from Dryad.⁷ There are two relevant searches that will return overlapping results:

- (1) Under the Data Links and Data Citations, you can select articles with DataCite DOIs in the full text (but **not** the bibliography). The articles found will include both those that are pointing to where their own data is archived and that are reusing archived data. It is not Dryad specific.
- (2) Under External Links, you can select articles with data in Dryad specifically. This is based on a list of article<->data package pairs that we provide to them, so includes links even when the article fails to include a reference to the dataset. But it does **not** include reuse citations.

⁷ EuropePMC DOI Link: http://www.researchinformation.info/news/news_story.php?news_id=1317

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It is now possible to search for papers that cite database records for several core life science databases, such as the European Nucleotide Archive, ArrayExpress, and PDB, as well as dataset DOIs used by, for example, Figshare and Dryad. As well as searching the Europe PMC website, RSS feeds can be created to alert a researcher when a particular dataset or data type has been cited. The SOAP and RESTful web services also provide third party services with access.⁸

This means that Europe PMC is providing direct links from articles to relevant externally-held information, and enables third parties to suggest relevant resources that enrich existing content. The External Links Service is a mechanism for people to publish links from articles in Europe PMC to related information or tools. It can be used to link databases, datasets, full text articles, community commentary or coursework too. The service has initially been made live with three providers: Dryad, which is a digital repository for the data underlying scientific publications; Train online, which provides free courses from EBI on Europe's most widely used data resources; and Bielefeld University Institutional Repository, which provides free-to-access article full text not otherwise available on Europe PMC.

2.3. arXiv

Integrations of both ORCID identifiers for authors, and DataCite DOIs for datasets associated with articles are on the arXiv roadmap. The increase in community understanding of the importance of such identifiers is leading to requests for them from users, from supporting institutions, and from collaborating services. At the time of writing, work is underway on integration with ORCID to associate authenticated ORCID iDs with arXiv user accounts. These identifiers will be used in data exports to enable others to connect arXiv data with author identities in their own systems. In

⁸ <http://europepmc.org/articles/PMC3667078>.

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addition, to better support institutions under arXiv's institutional membership model, it is hoped to use institutional affiliation information in authors' ORCID records to provide member institutions with statistics about contributions from their faculty.

Work to include DataCite DOIs for data in arXiv is still in the planning stages. Plans for integration at arXiv have evolved somewhat because of the greater use of reliable PIDs in other data repositories. Following ideas described in D3.3 section 4 it is intended that arXiv will assign DataCite DOIs to existing datasets in arXiv (stored using the "ancillary files" mechanism, http://arxiv.org/help/ancillary_files) and those to be migrated from the Data Conservancy pilot. Data stored in other relevant repositories, such as the one being developed as part of INSPIRE, will not be ingested or have a new DOI assigned. Instead such datasets will be associated with arXiv articles by reference only.

Involvement with ODIN and ORCID is influencing work on another major project at Cornell University Library, the home of arXiv. The Linked Data for Libraries (LD4L) project (see <https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/ld4l>), funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, is a partnership with Stanford and Harvard to explore the use of linked data techniques as a way to provide better library discovery systems spanning multiple institutions. Goals include the integration of information about authors and about items not traditionally included in library discovery systems. PIDs are clearly the best and easiest way to link to link references to the same entities in different systems, and URI forms of these (including ORCID iDs and DataCite DOIs) work very well with RDF. A challenge here will be the linking of librarian-created identifiers for people (e.g. ISNIs created from VIAF and other data sources) typically used with monographs, with ORCID iDs being used in journal article submission and associated with articles and data in repositories. Such linking holds the promise of unified views which include monograph, article, and data items, combined with information held in research information system profiles.

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3. COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

3.1. CERN codefest and 1st year event

All international partners participated in the first year event at CERN and in the codefest which took place just before. All partners contributed to the individual projects at the codefest. One project was HAMR⁹, dedicated to the Dryad-ORCID connection and got considerable results advancing the repository services.

The presence of the international partners allowed an extension of the discussion from the European perspectives to the global research communities. This was in particular evident when discussing the advancements in third party services based on PIDs such as altmetrics. ANDS moderated the final part of the 1st year event which underlined the global challenge in PID management and service development which demands a global collaborative effort to address this.

3.2. Open Repositories 2014

Open Repositories is the most important conference for repository developers, architects, and managers. The theme of Open Repositories 2014 was *"Towards Repository Ecosystems"*, a perfect match for ODIN work. It was held in Helsinki, Finland with over 450 attendees. Both the ODIN project and ORCID were strongly represented at the conference, and identifier interoperability was a hot topic.

⁹ <http://odin-project.eu/project-outputs/first-codesprint-oct-2013/>

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The ODIN panel “Promoting Interoperability and Services through Shared Identifiers” was very well attended and sparked ongoing discussions (see Figure 3).

Open Repositories 2014
June 9-13, Helsinki, Finland

Session Overview

Session

P7B: Parallel session 7B
 Time: Thursday, 12/Jun/2014: 11:15am - 12:30pm
 Session Chair: Michael Giarlo
 Panel

Location: Paasitorni - Siitasaari Hall
200 people

Session Abstract

The session has been recorded and is available for watching.

Presentations

Promoting Interoperability and Services Through Shared Identifiers
 Suenje Dallmeier-Tiessen¹, Laura Paglione², Sebastian Peters³, Ryan Scherle⁴
¹CERN; ²ORCID; ³DataCite; ⁴Dryad Digital Repository

This panel proposes a technical discussion on the use of persistent identifiers as a support for interoperable research platforms and the services built on top of them.

Speakers from ORCID and DataCite will discuss implementation challenges for persistent identifier registries, including community engagement and support for development of third party services. Dryad and CERN will focus on the challenges and opportunities for integrating shared persistent identifiers.

Figure 3: Open Repositories 2014 programme entry for ODIN panel discussion

A “developer challenge” has been a popular fixture in the Open Repositories programme for the past few years. It is designed to encourage collaboration between developers and designers from different institutions and organizations on topics of interest to the community. The challenge this year was to *“Build or enhance a repository ecosystem, in line with the conference themes”*. This year ODIN sponsored the competition and encouraged works on shared identifiers (see Figures 4 and 5).

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Developer Challenge

Posted on 22.5.2014 by Joonas Kesäniemi – No Comments ↓

Update: [More info about how to enter – what you have to do](#)

Update: See the [ideas page](#) for suggestions of what you could work on.

Update – more prizes!!!

- Best use of Fedora 4: \$250 USD Amazon Gift voucher
- ODIN will provide a prize of an iPad to the "best" project, *as determined by a vote of the participating developers*. The EC-funded ODIN project (<http://odin-project.eu>) builds on the ORCID and DataCite initiatives to uniquely identify researchers and data sets and connect this information across multiple services and infrastructures for scholarly communication. ODIN aims to address critical open questions including referencing data objects, tracking of data use and re-use, and linking between a data object, subsets, articles, rights statements and every person involved in its life-cycle.

Figure 4: Open Repositories 2014 developer challenge description

Interoperability and services through shared identifiers

Overview

Shared identifier infrastructures, such as DOIs for research objects and ORCIDs for research persons, can improve interoperability, allow for increased efficiency of internal processes, and facilitate the development of innovative third-party services.

This development challenge is to use the open APIs provided by DataCite and ORCID to build an application or service based on these persistent, shared, and open identifiers.

A non-exclusive list of possible areas on which to focus:

- Data author discovery or disambiguation
- Tracking institutional output
- Curation or collaboration tools
- Linking related research objects
- Tracking of citations or alternative metrics to data
- Allowing personal repositories to take advantage of ID systems

Figure 5: ODIN's project proposal for the Open Repositories 2014 developer challenge

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The winner of the ODIN prize was Tom Johnson (Oregon State University, USA) who demonstrated integration of ORCID into the Sufia institutional repository system based on the popular Ruby/Hydra platform.¹⁰

In the rest of the Open Repositories, there were four addition presentations that focused on ORCID or DataCite DOIs, and a Monday workshop devoted to integration of ORCID iDs in repository workflows.

The international partners (Dryad, arXiv and ANDS) were represented at OR14 so that informal ODIN meetings took place to organize the final ODIN reports, i.e. joint publications which would underpin ODIN's international communication strategy.

3.3. Social Media contributions

Based on the communications and outreach strategy of the ODIN project. International partners contributed or lead-authored blog posts on the ODIN page. ANDS for example lead the blog post about the Research Data Alliance Meeting in Dublin (March 2014). In addition, results and events were disseminated further via international partners' tweets.

¹⁰ Code is on github: <https://github.com/no-reply/sufia-demo-app>

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4. FEEDBACK ON FINAL OUTPUTS OF ODIN WORKING PACKAGES

This section presents the feedback of the Australian and US partners on the ODIN final outputs of WP3, WP4, and WP5. Each of the year-two deliverables (D3.3, D4.2 and D5.2) has been reviewed and is discussed. Discussion of the year-one deliverables (D3.1, D3.2, D4.1 and D5.1) are taken verbatim from D6.1 to provide a complete picture. The discussion for each deliverable is consolidated from feedback provided by ANDS, arXiv and DRYAD.

4.1. Human and the Social Science (HSS) Proof of Concept (D3.1)

This proof of concept study focused on adopting identifiers for British Birth Cohort Studies, longitudinal studies that are funded by the UK's Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) and Medical Research Council (MRC). The D3.1 report describes the state of persistent identifier adaptation in the area of humanities and social science; in addition, it outlines the preliminary models and workflows to be explored and developed upon in year two of ODIN.

As part of the ODIN project, Australian Data Archive has provided insights into the global social science data archive landscape, especially with regard to commonalities between data providers across the world. This international perspective was enhanced with conversations with data providers such as GESIS in Germany and ICPSR in the USA.

4.2. High-Energy Physics (HEP) Proof of Concept (D3.2)

The D3.2 report -- first year report on the HEP proof of concept -- investigated the challenges and the need for identifiers in the domain of high

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energy physics. It focused on preliminary models and workflows for metadata exchange in this domain, to support the activities in the second year of the ODIN project for this community.

The report highlighted two key challenges in this domain: managing authorship, and aggregating information from multiple datacentres. The high number of authors on some papers within this domain (e.g papers with more than 3,000 authors) and the fact that the information about publications and underlying datasets are derived from multiple data centres pose difficult challenges for author disambiguation.

The report described significant work in understanding data modelling and mapping between different services in the HEP scholarly communication ecosystem. While developing an extensible model, the report focused on concrete workflows sharing data between INSPIRE and the arXiv and HepData services. The analysis provided guidance for improvement of interfaces, data structures and services in year two of ODIN, beyond the existing *ad hoc* links between INSPIRE, arXiv and HepData.

4.3. Proof of Concept and Commonality (D3.3)

The D3.3 report builds on the work reported in D3.1 and D3.2 from the first year. It reports and details completion of the analysis of commonalities and differences between the High Energy Physics (HEP) and Human and Social Science (HSS) fields. Documentation of current practices and technical approaches in these fields provides a broad view of community needs and common issues in open and interoperable permanent identifiers of data and contributors. The work in HSS was extended with

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inclusion of the Survey of Health and Development (NSHD)¹¹ in the UK through use of their implementation of DOIs and author IDs.

The report succeeds in meeting the key WP3 goal of deriving a “*common cross-disciplinary view on the relevant workflows*”. Perhaps the best summary of this is the refined generic workflow developed through consideration of the similarities and differences between the proofs of concept, and this is illustrated in Figure 6 (from D3.3).

Figure 6: Refined generic workflow showing connections to ORCID and DataCite systems at different points (D3.3 Figure Y)

It is significant that this workflow that has been shown to apply to the processes at very diverse disciplinary data centres, even though different techniques may be used to implement the workflow. Differences in technical implementations are driven by differences in the conceptual details of the repositories, such as whether a repository primarily aggregates content or receives direct deposits from researchers, and whether it stores discrete data packages or uses a relational database. The ability to derive a generic workflow is also a validation that development of the DataCite and ORCID architectures and web services have already been successful in enabling this

¹¹ LHA National Survey of Health and Development: <http://www.nshd.mrc.ac.uk/>

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cross-discipline adoption. The understanding of the generic workflow and criteria by which services decide how to deploy identifiers within it will be of significant utility to those investigating the use of author and data identifiers in existing or new systems.

4.4. Conceptual Model of Interoperability (D4.1)

The D4.1 report focuses on the four main challenges of persistent identifiers by ORCID and DataCite including accessibility, discovery, interoperability and sustainability. The report presents the state of the art identification systems, and proposed a conceptual model to solve the interoperability between different identifiers for data and people. The proposed model uses a trusted identifier layer to mint and manage identifiers for data and authors. The model is exemplified by the use of ORCID and DataCite services to mint and link researcher identifiers and Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) for data.

The proposed model by ODIN is aligned with the existing infrastructure in ANDS services and Research Data Australia. In 2011, ANDS provided support for minting DOI. More recently, ANDS implemented ORCID integration [3], enabling Australian researchers to use the trusted identifier layer to link and disseminate their datasets at the international level.

arXiv has long maintained authority records tied to author accounts and in 2008 introduced local author identifiers. Following the model proposed by ODIN, arXiv works on the integration with ORCID to connect local author identities with ORCID iDs for interoperability. arXiv will also create DataCite DOIs for ancillary data files using the EZID service, and these data files will be linked to the ORCID iDs of their authors.

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Dryad has minted DataCite DOIs for its data since 2010 but has so far lacked the ability to recognize when authors on different datasets correspond to the same person. ODIN has helped inform development work now underway to allow user accounts to be linked to ORCID IDs, to enable co-authors editing privileges to datasets via their ORCID identities, and to publicly index ORCIDs for data authors in the DataCite Metadata Store.

4.5. Workflow for interoperability (D4.2)

Interoperability of identifiers systems is a crucial enabler for smoother and more enhanced services that could work across disciplinary, national or institutional boundaries. Based on the work conducted in the first year, the final tasks expanded on the PID harmonization and focused on real implementations that would translate the conceptual model into real first services. The public exposure and discussion of these tools underlined their use to the international community.

As part of the work, similarities between ANDS and EThOS platforms were found. This concerns the aggregating metadata from multiple registries with heterogeneous identifiers. The ANDS experience in this domain shows that lack of connectivity between these identifiers can lead to duplicated records in national registries such as Research Data Australia (ANDS supported portal for the Australian Research Data Commons). In addition, lack of harmonisation between these identifiers hinders the connectedness of research projects (grants) and research outcomes. There is still a lot of work to do in this regard, which is already being addressed in a dedicated working group lead by ANDS with the support of CERN and Dryad.

The ISNI claiming tool is a good showcase to underline the potential of a better ORCID-ISNI collaboration. Given the parallel developments and overlap of the works, there are remaining challenges to be addressed. It is, for example needed to scale up

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the linking. Furthermore, it is necessary to expose and share rich links to works embedded in the ISNI data model. This will provide a basis for expanding links to other research works and datasets. Considering searches and discoverability, further advancements are needed as well: for example to search the ISNI database using ORCID metadata and post the ISNI on the ORCID record.

The conclusions of this deliverable underline that ODIN has facilitated the interoperability of PIDs in practice which needs to be expanded upon. Results need to be scaled up and stress tested in large scale research environments and e-infrastructure settings. A so called "light-weight" approach, based on the ORCID and DataCite, is expected to deliver the best results when scaling up. The results underline that a trusted, sustainable PID system can serve as a hub to connect disparate identifiers, profiles, metadata and platforms. This is promising in the international scale where the scenarios and use cases might become even more complex. A light weight approach enables easier integration - each service, platform and community is then free to pursue the use-cases that matter to them, supported by, and connected to the wider scholarly information network via the hub.

4.6. Gap Analysis and Roadmap (D5.1 and D5.2)

Roadmap and recommendations for the missing thin layer of the e-Infrastructure

The final key set of outputs reviewed by the international partners were the *Draft gap analysis and roadmap* (D5.1) report and the *Final roadmap and recommendations for the missing thin layer of the e-Infrastructure* (D5.2) report. The WP5 reports (D5.1 and D5.2) focus on the roadmap toward enabling a global and open discoverability of data and other scholarly materials. The combined reports highlight the need for a global interoperable data exchange framework, and the key

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role of identifiers in linking researchers to their work and encouraging data citation and data sharing.

The roadmap identifies the key stakeholders who are heavily involved in the design, implementation and adoption of the persistent identifiers including e-infrastructure operators, funders, policy maker, publishers and libraries. Aligned with the ODIN vision, ANDS has been liaising with these stakeholders to establish persistent, transparent and sustainable connections among research data, publications, researchers and research grants. In addition, ANDS has been actively working with the community to make the research data connected, reusable, managed and discoverable. These objectives addresses the same issues that has been identified by the ODIN gap analysis report including

Gap 1: There is only limited access to e-infrastructures for small institutions or interest groups.

A large number of mostly small organizations are not yet part of an international interdisciplinary scientific e-infrastructure. However, for PI systems to have the greatest impact on discoverability and open science, they need to be broadly implemented. Thus, access to e-infrastructures and PI systems has to be facilitated across large and small organizations.

- The experience from ANDS, arXiv and Dryad shows that there is an infrastructure gap in research sector at the domain, national and international levels.
- Despite significant federal funding in this area, there are still a major need to enabling e-infrastructure in small research institutions and creating interoperability between universities across countries and continents.

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Gap 2: There are research communities that have none to little experience with interoperable PIs.

For some communities, experience with PIs has been largely with DOIs for publications. PIs for authors or scholarly materials are not well established.

- ANDS investment for building the culture of data citation in Australia shows that a significant coordination and effort in research community is required for knowledge sharing and awareness.
- Libraries and research offices play important role in assisting researchers in using identifiers for citation. However, these resources are very limited.

Gap 3: There are research communities that have built local PI systems.

While local solutions can be customized to the needs of a specific community, they are not interoperable with other systems and therefore cannot overcome disciplinary or national boundaries. This is a severe barrier to discoverability and access.

- arXiv and Dryad both have engaged with domain specific communities, and their experience shows that often local PI systems requires custom solutions for enabling interoperability to national and international infrastructures.
- ANDS funding in Australia has supported a number of interoperability projects in this domain; however, there is a need for a national coordination to make these systems work beyond the boundaries of a single continent.

Gap 4: There is a lack of support and funding to implement international standards.

Organizations that would like to be part of a global PI based e-infrastructure may lack money and expertise to implement PI systems and/or standards to link their local services with interoperable systems. There has to be dedicated funding to encourage institutions to get engaged in PI infrastructures.

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- In US the research fund provided through the National Science Foundation provides the initial support for creating research infrastructure projects; however, sustainability of these services is a challenge through the project funding model.
- In Australia, the sustainability of the e-infrastructure is often managed by the hosting research institutions; however, this model is not scalable and often put pressure on universities, leading to the need for Australian government continuous effort to improve the sustainability of research infrastructures.

Gap 5: Methods and tools to track re-use of research data and other scholarly materials are lacking.

Currently researchers cannot track the use and re-use of their shared data. PI systems can enable tools that track the re-use of these data sets and further incentivize data sharing through attribution and citation.

- ANDS has invested in metadata exchange with the Thomson Reuters data citation index. However, this project is still at the early stages and more work is required in this domain. Also ANDS is working toward interoperability projects with other ODIN partners including Dryad, CERN and DataCite.

Gap 6: Policies to encourage data sharing and acknowledge re-use in the grant review process are nascent.

A major component of the grant review process is an assessment of the impact of prior work. However, without metrics to measure the use and reuse of data sets (Gap 5), these important research contributions cannot be included in the review process.

- The experience from the international partners shows that there is need for better policies in this area. The funders and policy makers have a significant role in improving data sharing through encouraging the culture of data citation.

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Gap 7: Reliable discovery services for research data and non-text based scholarly materials are missing.

Research data is currently accessed via disciplinary data repositories. This can hinder cross-disciplinary discovery and re-use of research data. Integration of PI systems in the disciplinary systems can enable cross-platform discovery services and search portals.

- In the last few years, ANDS has provided project fund to a number of Australian research organisations to develop institutional repositories, aiming to reduce the gap in this area. However, more development is required to provide adequate coverage across all fields of research.
- Dryad and arXiv are participants in the Data Description Registry Interoperability WG in Research Data Alliance and Dryad is collaborating with ANDS to enable cross-platform discovery between their services. The results of these interoperability projects can lead to better understanding of the gaps in this area.

Gap 8: Incentives for making datasets re-usable are unclear or missing.

While data repositories offer citation recommendations for research datasets, in practice, the research data are rarely cited. Data citation needs to be facilitated and incentive systems for data citation need to be agreed on and developed otherwise data sharing will be hindered.

- ANDS has invested in this area through the ANDS capability program including hosting workshops, webinars and conference presentations. Although the ANDS investment in Australia provided capabilities in universities to support the culture of data citation, there is a need for a holistic approach for developing the culture of data sharing and data citation.

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Gap 9: Value-added services that can incentivize citation and open science require an interoperable PI infrastructure.

Although all actors are highly aware that value-added services for the scholarly community are needed, the lack of widely adopted interoperable PIs makes it difficult if not impossible to create local or global value-added services.

- The experience from ANDS, Dryad and arXiv shows that the lack of international adoption of author and data identifiers hinders the productivity of value-added services.

Gap 10: Unique attribution and linking between researchers, their scholarly materials and funding will only be possible with the collaborative adoption of global and interoperable PI systems.

Research assessment depends on citation of scholarly materials, attribution of contributors, and linkages with the grants that funded the work. Datacite, FundRef, and ORCID provide an example of how organizations can work together to address this gap and the potential benefit of more general adoption of interoperable PI systems.

- The ANDS services leverage the interoperability between DataCite, ORCID and other supporting platforms such as FundRef and CrossRef. The ANDS experience in this area shows that the interoperability between these services is vital for creating successful research infrastructures at the national and international levels.

The following tables summarises the perspective of the international partners on the ODIN gap analysis and identified further actions and beneficiaries at the international level.

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ODIN Gap Analysis	International perspective	Actions and Beneficiaries
<p>Gap 1: There is only limited access to e-infrastructures for small institutions or interest groups.</p>	<p>Universally relevant :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - long tail of research is not necessarily catered for by national scale infrastructure - disciplinary repositories such as arXiv & Dryad may provide support to all members of a community 	<p>Lower access barriers for institutions to be part of interoperable PI e-infrastructures. These institutions and any individual researcher need to have access to an interoperable open PI framework. Measures must be put in place either through institutions, collaborations or national / international bodies.</p> <p>These actions support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small research institutions and universities, long tail of research - e-infrastructure providers
<p>Gap 2: There are research communities that have little or no experience with interoperable persistent identifiers.</p>	<p>Shared international concern:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RDA working group formed to help address this issue - awareness raising and support is an increasing priority, e.g. in the Australian strategy (National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy) and the ORCID Adoption and Integration Program 	<p>Support those scientific communities without identifiers to become part of the described trustworthy, sustainable and interoperable framework.</p> <p>These actions support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - research communities - individual researchers

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<p>Gap 3: There are research communities that have built local PI systems.</p>	<p>Widespread phenomenon</p>	<p>Engage those stakeholders with community-, institution- or nation-specific identifiers and support their opening and collaboration with others.</p> <p>These actions provide value to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - e-infrastructure providers - research communities - individual researchers - funders
<p>Gap 4: There is a lack of support and funding to implement international standards.</p>	<p>Significant obstacle worldwide, but at least partly overcome by organizations such as ORCID and DataCite that can leverage resources in many different countries and have distributed long-term revenue streams.</p>	<p>Provide low-barrier dedicated funding to implement international standards.</p> <p>These actions support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - e-infrastructure providers
<p>Gap 5: Methods and tools to track re-use of research data and other scholarly materials are lacking.</p>	<p>Critical for global information systems. Sufficient public infrastructure investment can help spur the development of both nonprofit (e.g. ImpactStory.org) and commercial</p>	<p>Develop an interoperable PI infrastructure that allows the development of tools that are built on top of the scholarly output, e.g. track research data re-use.</p>

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	(e.g. Thomson Reuters Data Citation Index) infrastructure.	These actions provide value to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - research communities - individual researchers - funders
Gap 6: Policies to encourage data sharing and acknowledge re-use in the grant review process are nascent.	Ongoing transnational concern - US National Science Foundation and National Institutes of Health have made significant first steps in this regard.	Provide incentives for open science, e.g. citation mechanisms including PIs for any scholarly material. These actions provide value to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - individual researchers
Gap 7: Reliable discovery services for research data and non text-based scholarly materials are missing.	Significant international lacuna - RDA working group formed through ODIN leadership	Developing new policies that support data reuse and data sharing These actions provide value to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - individual researchers - funders
Gap 8: Incentives for making datasets re-usable are unclear or missing.	As for gap 5	As for gap 5

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<p>Gap 9: Value-added services that can incentivize citation and open science require an interoperable PI infrastructure.</p>	<p>Important international opportunity, with considerable experimentation underway in nonprofit and private sectors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - e.g. Mendeley, Dryad, Figshare 	<p>Provide low-barrier dedicated funding to develop value-added services</p> <p>These actions provide value to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - e-infrastructure providers - individual researchers
<p>Gap 10: Unique attribution and linking between researchers, their scholarly materials and funding will only be possible with the collaborative adoption of global and interoperable PI systems.</p>	<p>Underlying global concern</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience within the very successful collaborations between INSPIRE, arXiv, and ADS has highlighted the need for interoperable PIs to match identities between systems. 	<p>Establish a framework with PIs for authors/contributors and materials.</p> <p>These actions provide value to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - e-infrastructure providers - individual researchers - funders

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5. SUMMARY

In this report, we have presented how ODIN interoperability approach aligns with other international activities in this area. In addition, we have discussed how the collaboration between DataCite, ORCID and other ODIN partners has initiated a number of activities towards building a layer of interoperability between identifiers. The scope of these activities highlights the importance and versatility of ODIN interoperability model, and suggests that presented proof of concept projects can be further developed to benefit extended community.

ODIN gap analysis and roadmap shows that there are a number of areas that requires planning and special attention of policy makers, research institutions and funding bodies in order to create a seamless integration of identifiers into research ecosystems. As discussed in this report, the experience by ANDS and other international partners show that there is a need for developing technical capabilities, best practice approaches and training for the research community to enable using unique identifiers and use these identifiers to link the scholarly work. The gap analysis by ODIN partners provided a cohesive list of requirements for future development of e-infrastructure and interoperability projects in the research sector.

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